

A Simple Method for Determination of Intrinsic Viscosity of Dilute Polymer Solutions

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Viscosity measurement of dilute polymer solutions in thermodynamically good solvents is considered to be very important and is widely practised both in research laboratories and in industries for determination of average molecular weight of polymers. The Mark-Houwink relationship between viscosity of a polymer solution and its average molecular weight is given by

$$[\eta] = K\bar{M}_v^a$$

Now the 'intrinsic viscosity', $[\eta]$, is defined by

$$[\eta] = \lim_{c \rightarrow 0} \left(\frac{\eta - \eta_0}{\eta_0 c} \right) = \lim_{c \rightarrow 0} \left(\frac{t - t_0}{t_0 c} \right) = \lim_{c \rightarrow 0} \left(\frac{\Delta t}{t_0 c} \right)$$

where η , η_0 and t , t_0 are the viscosities and times of flow of polymer solution and pure solvent through viscometer, respectively. Therefore the usual practice for the determination of $[\eta]$ is to find out the $(\Delta t/t_0)_c$ of the polymer solution for at least three different concentrations and then extrapolated to zero concentration. This time-consuming process can be eliminated by the preparation of a standard calibration curve, or otherwise¹. If the temperature of viscosity measurement, concentration of polymer solution, and the polymer-solvent pair are kept constant, then

$$\left(\frac{\Delta t}{t_0} \right)_c \propto [\eta]$$

and a plot of $(\Delta t/t_0)_c$ vs. $[\eta]$ will provide a straight line. To prepare the calibration curve for a given polymer-solvent pair at a particular concentration of the polymer solution, $[\eta]$, obtained by the usual method of extrapolation, is plotted against $(\Delta t/t_0)_c$. Once the calibration curve is ready, the $[\eta]$ of unknown solutions is easily obtained by determining the $(\Delta t/t_0)_c$ at one concentration only and taking the corresponding value of $[\eta]$ from the calibration graph. For different polymer-solvent pairs, or of the same polymer-solvent pair at different tem-

1. Gerner *et al.*, *Chem. Abs.*, 1965, 63, 3049c.

perature, different calibration curves should be prepared. Fig. 1 represents the calibration curve of polymethylmethacrylate (unfractionated) in benzene at 30°, $(\Delta t/t_0)_c$ being measured at $c=0.2$ g./dl in an ordinary Ostwald viscometer.

FIG. 1

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